

Sample Name: dNMPs 400uM -P-3 50x

```

=====
Acq. Operator   : SYSTEM                      Seq. Line :    3
Sample Operator : SYSTEM
Acq. Instrument : HPLC-UV-FC                 Location  :    3
Injection Date  : 1/8/2021 12:48:52 PM      Inj       :    1
                                           Inj Volume: 50.000 µl
Method          : C:\Users\Public\Documents\ChemStation\3\Data\dNMP to dNTP yield 2021-01-08
                  11-55-26\dNTP QUANTIFICATION.M (Sequence Method)
Last changed    : 12/10/2020 6:09:05 PM by SYSTEM
=====
    
```


Fraction Information

No Fractions found.

Area Percent Report

```

Sorted By      : Signal
Multiplier     : 1.0000
Dilution      : 1.0000
Do not use Multiplier & Dilution Factor with ISTDs
    
```

Signal 1: VWD1 A, Wavelength=254 nm

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	1.882	BB	0.0589	10.38350	2.73356	0.3888
2	2.080	BV R	0.0577	38.17188	10.33067	1.4294
3	2.176	VV E	0.0515	6.18535	1.81287	0.2316
4	2.251	VB	0.0479	9.02195	2.90640	0.3378
5	2.412	BV	0.0767	13.57304	2.54661	0.5083
6	2.596	VV R	0.0985	35.28972	5.26908	1.3215

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```

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
7	6.243	BB	0.1453	30.09148	3.18137	1.1268
8	8.324	BB	0.2021	59.55677	4.46833	2.2302
9	9.799	BB	0.1741	38.92931	3.44281	1.4578
10	10.477	BV	0.1790	244.40460	20.85282	9.1522
11	10.924	VB	0.1699	85.68502	7.65711	3.2087
12	12.944	BV R	0.1768	457.23373	39.62487	17.1221
13	13.478	VB E	0.1812	91.86687	7.71004	3.4401
14	14.791	BB	0.1857	307.86703	25.29736	11.5287
15	16.271	BB	0.1859	628.26685	51.54237	23.5268
16	18.450	BB	0.1932	613.90637	48.85528	22.9890

Totals : 2670.43349 238.23156

```
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*** End of Report ***
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